

PREPARATION OF ANALYSIS OF LEARNING TASKS FOR THE SKILL OF MAKING FLOWER BOUQUETS MADE OF PIPE CLEANERS FOR CHILDREN WITH MILD INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES IN CLASS IX AT SLB BC YPLAB WARTAWAN BANDUNG

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Abstract

Children with mild intellectual disabilities have intelligence far below the average of children in general, so in the learning process they have difficulties in understanding global instructions, to overcome this can be done through task analysis, which contains more detailed task details. The purpose of this study is to compile an analysis of learning tasks for the skill of making flower bouquets made of pipe cleaners for children with mild intellectual disabilities in class IX at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City. The method used in this study is a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. This data was obtained through; observation, interviews, documentation studies, FGD (Focus Group Discussion), and validation. Data analysis techniques start from data reduction, data display, conclusion and verification. The subjects in this study are 5 (five) children with mild intellectual disabilities and 1 (one) skill teacher. The results of the research were obtained in the form of a learning program in the form of task analysis that contained the steps to make a flower bouquet, starting from getting to know the tools and materials, the steps of making a flower bouquet, maintaining tools and materials, and maintaining the results. Recommendations are given to teachers to have insight to be able to compile task analysis, so that they can help children with mild intellectual disabilities in understanding the learning material delivered by the teacher.

Keywords: Mild Intellectual Disability, Task Analysis Preparation, Skills, Bouquet of Flowers, Pipe, Cleaner.

INTRODUCTION

Children with mild intellectual disabilities are part of Children with Special Needs (ABK). Children with mild intellectual disabilities have special educational needs. They need a learning approach that suits their learning abilities and needs. This is in accordance with the opinion found by Munzayanah (2000:22) that "Children with mild intellectual disabilities are those who still have the possibility of obtaining education in the fields of reading, writing, and arithmetic at a certain level in special schools". Usually for the group they can reach a certain level, the level of grade IV of elementary school, and can learn simple skills.

According to Wantah (2007:10) in Louk and Sukoco, (2016:26) that:

Children who are classified as mild mental retardation or mild intellectual disability, are children who can only learn skills and academic levels up to grade 6 of elementary school (SD). Children with mild intellectual disabilities have the ability to speak, but the vocabulary of words is very lacking. The lack of vocabulary results in children with mild intellectual

disabilities having difficulty thinking abstractly, but children with mild intellectual disabilities can participate in education both in elementary school and in special schools part C (SLB/C). For example, a child who is 16 years old, the child's intelligence age has only reached the same level of intelligence age as a 12-year-old child.

Children with mild intellectual disabilities in the learning process have difficulty understanding instructions that are global or large as stated in the teaching module, as a result of which children with mild intellectual disabilities have difficulty understanding the learning materials delivered by the teacher. To overcome this, it can be done through task analysis, where the learning material can be detailed as simply as possible so that it can make it easier for children to understand the learning material.

Task analysis can make it easier to decipher the components of the task unit that are considered difficult, so that children with mild intellectual disabilities can understand the learning series that has been adjusted to their abilities. Complex skills can be very burdensome, but task analysis breaks them down into achievable steps, by mastering each step, the child gains confidence and motivation to handle more complex tasks, resulting in long-term skill acquisition, and can master tasks or activities more effectively.

According to Sudrajar & Rodida (2013:101) "task analysis is a technique of breaking down a task or activity into small steps in sequence and teaching each step so that children can do it all". Meanwhile, according to the opinion of Rochayadi and Alimin (2005:126), "task analysis is work that is summarized with specific work units".

The advantage for teachers when using teacher task analysis is that they can set realistic learning goals, design appropriate learning programs, adjust teaching methods, materials according to the child's level of understanding and can develop various skills such as cutting, shaping and stringing.

The research conducted by Aini and Iswari (2019) was titled "The Effectiveness of Task Analysis in Improving Fish Cracker Making Skills for Children with Mild Intellectual Disabilities". The study uses an experimental method in the form of a pre-experimental design with a type of one group pretest-posttest design consisting of three stages, namely pretest, treatment and posttest. With a subject consisting of 5 (five) children. The results of the study concluded that the average score taken before being given the treatment (*pre-test*) and after receiving the consequences of the treatment (*posttest*) increased by 15%.

This means that the child already has a good ability in the skill of making fish crackers, after being treated with task analysis. This is in line with a study conducted by Rislaela (2019) entitled "The Effectiveness of Task Analysis Techniques in Improving Button-Down Clothing Skills in Students with Mild Intellectual Disabilities". The study uses a single subject research method with an ABA design. The results of the study showed that there was an increase in children's skills in wearing button-down clothes, as evidenced by an increase *in the mean level* in the baseline-1 (A-1) condition by 60.5%, the intervention condition (B) by 75.18%, and the *baseline-2 (A-2) condition* by 83.33%.

The results of a preliminary study conducted by researchers at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City found a problem that the skill program for making flower bouquets made of *pipe cleaners* has not been in the form of task analysis.

Based on the results of the preliminary study, the researcher is interested in conducting a research entitled "Preparation of Analysis of Learning Tasks for Making Flower Bouquets Made of *Pipe Cleaner* for Children with Mild Intellectual Disabilities Class IX at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City".

RESEARCH METHODS

The selection and determination of the type of method is very important so that the research objectives can be achieved and a formula can be obtained.

1. Research Methods

The research method is a procedure to obtain data in a research. The research method used in this study is a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. The selection of this method is in accordance with the purpose of the research where the research wants to reveal the problems that are currently occurring, without any data engineering obtained in the field, namely about "Preparation of Analysis of the Learning Task of Making Flower Bouquets Made of *Pipe Cleaner* for Children with Mild Intellectual Disabilities Class IX at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City".

According to Ramdhan (2021:17) that "Descriptive research is research with a method to describe the results of a research". This type of descriptive research has the purpose of providing a description or explanation of the matter being researched.

2. Research Approach

The research approach is a design of a research to be carried out, and the design is used to get answers to the research questions formulated. As in the research, a qualitative approach is used.

According to Sugiyono (2019:18) the qualitative research method is "A research method based on the philosophy of postpositivism, used to research on natural object conditions, (as opposed to experiments) where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out". This research is descriptive and tends to use data analysis. The process and meaning (subject perspective) are more highlighted in qualitative research.

3. Data Collection Techniques

In this study, the data collection technique uses several methods, as follows:

a. Observation

Observation is an accurate and easy method of data collection, aiming to explore data on children's ability to learn to make flower bouquets. According to Gulo (2002:116) "Observation is a data collection method where researchers record information as they witness during research. Observation involves two components, namely the observer or observer and the

object being observed."

From the explanation above, it can be concluded that observation is a data collection method that involves the observer and the object being observed.

b. Interview

Interviews are used as a data collection technique to find information about the teaching materials currently used by teachers for children with mild intellectual disabilities in grade IX. According to Saroso (2017:47) "Interviews are one of the most widely used tools to collect qualitative research data."

Based on the explanation above, the interview is a two-way communication to obtain information from the relevant respondents. It can also be said that an interview is a face-to-face conversation between the interviewer and the source, where the interviewer asks directly about an object that has been researched and has been designed in advance.

c. Documentation Studies

Documentation studies are data collection by studying and studying regulations, books and documentation that have a reference to the problem being researched. Regarding documentation, according to Sugiyono (2018:476), it is "a method used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, writing numbers and drawings in the form of reports and information that can support research."

Based on the above statement, it can be concluded that documentation is a way or source of data used in research to obtain information in the form of books, archives, documents, writing numbers and pictures.

d. FGD (*Focus Group Discussion*)

Focus Group Discussion / FGD or focus group discussion is a data collection method that is commonly used in social qualitative research, including research in the field of education. This is in line with Lehoux, Poland, & Daudelin, (2006) (in Afyanti, 2008:59)

The FGD method is one of the research data collection methods with the final result providing data derived from the interaction of a number of participants in a study, like most other data collection methods. The FGD method has a number of characteristics, including, it is a data collection method for the type of qualitative research and the data produced comes from the exploration of social interactions that occur during the discussion process carried out by the informants involved. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that *Focus Group Discussion* (FGD) is one of the qualitative data collection techniques made to obtain very specific information or data through group discussions.

e. Validation

Validation is an appropriate act of proof where all aspects (processes, materials, activities) must be in accordance with expectations. According to Arikunto (2006:156) that "a measure that shows the validity or validity of an instrument." Based on the explanation above, validation is

defined as an act of proving in an appropriate way that each material, process, procedure, activity, system, equipment or mechanism used in production and supervision will always achieve the desired results.

4. Data Analysis

Data analysis is a method or way to process data into information so that the characteristics of the data become easy to understand and also useful for finding solutions to problems, which are mainly problems about a research. In this study, the data analysis technique used is the data analysis technique from Miles and Huuberman (1984) (in Sugiyono, 2018:246), which is "carried out interactively and lasts continuously until the completion of activities in analyzing data in qualitative research, namely data reduction, *data display*, and conclusion or verification". The analysis used in this study consists of three components, which are as follows:

a. Data Reduction

Data reduction is a form of analysis that sharpens, classifies, directs, discards the unnecessary, and organizes data in such a way that conclusions can finally be drawn and verified. According to Sugiyono (2018:337) that "the data obtained in the field is certainly quite large and in a form that is not as real as quantitative data. Therefore, data reduction is summarizing, choosing the main things, focusing on the important things and looking for themes, patterns and discarding the unnecessary".

b. Display Data

Once the data is reduced, the next step is to display the data. In this case, Miles and Huberman (1984) in Sugiyono (2017: 137) state that "What is most often used to present data in qualitative research is with narrative texts." In this data display stage, the data categories that have been created in the reduction stage are arranged into sequences so that the structure can be understood.

c. Conclusion and Verification

Drawing conclusions is the last process of the steps carried out above. The third step in qualitative data analysis according to Miles and Huberman (1992:18) is "Drawing conclusions and verifying". The initial conclusions presented are still provisional, and will change if no strong supporting evidence is found at the next stage of data collection. However, if the conclusions presented in the early stages are supported by valid and consistent evidence when the researcher returns to the field to collect data, then the conclusions presented are credible conclusions.

5. Research Subject

The subjects in this study are 5 (five) children with mild intellectual disabilities in grade IX at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City, 1 (one) skill teacher, and 1 (one) classroom teacher, as well as 2 (two) teachers, as validators from SLB Al-Hikmat and SLB Bina Kasih Bandung City.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion in this study are as follows:

1. Research Results

Based on the observation results of this study, several meetings were held to see children's learning abilities. Observations were made by researchers when children were learning these skills, the following data were obtained; 3 (three) children can get to know the tools used in making flower bouquets, while 2 (two) children are not able to know the tools, because children are easily distracted by the surrounding environment and easily bored. In the section on getting to know the materials, 3 (three) children can get to know the materials used in making a bouquet of flowers, while 2 (two) children cannot recognize the materials because some of the materials have the same shape which results in frequent confusion, besides that the child's focus is easily distracted.

The results of interviews with skills teachers, the program used at this time is in the form of a teaching module, which contains instructions on the steps to make a flower bouquet in general, not yet detailed, resulting in a lack of understanding of the basics of making flower bouquets because the teacher teaches children directly to the core of learning.

The results of the documentation study obtained include; teaching modules, children's ability data, report card scores, and photos of activities.

FGD (*Focus Group Discussion*) was conducted by 5 (five) students, 1 (one) skills teacher, and 1 (one) classroom teacher. From the results of the discussion, a form of task analysis was obtained starting from getting to know the tools, getting to know the materials, the steps of making a flower bouquet, maintaining tools and materials, and maintaining the results. The preparation of the task analysis began by determining the learning material on the skill of making a flower bouquet made of *pipe cleaner* for children with mild intellectual disabilities in grade IX.

Validation of the results of the analysis of the skill learning task of making a flower bouquet made of pipe cleaner was carried out by 1 (one) skill teacher at SLB Hikmat Bandung City and 1 (one) skill teacher at SLB Bina Kasih Bandung City.

The 1st (first) validator from the skills teacher at SLB BC Bina Kasih Bandung City gave his response that in the table for the preparation of the task analysis of the implementation part, it is necessary to add a sentence applying K3 (occupational health and safety) in the use of dangerous tools during the work on the flower bouquet. In addition, the 1st (first) validator in the implementation aspect added the sentence "cut the styrofoam that has been divided into two parts into four parts" and in the aspect of maintaining materials, added the sentence "clean the used skill room".

The 2nd (second) validator from the skills teacher at SLB Hikmat Bandung City, suggested clarifying the sentence of the task statement on the sub-aspect of distinguishing tools and materials. Validators also gave suggestions to arrange aspects of the instrument according to categories, such as tools with tools and materials with materials.

Table 1: Analysis of the Task of Making a Bouquet Made of *Pipe Cleaner* for Children with Mild Intellectual Disabilities Class Ix at Slb Yplab Wartawan Bandung

N o.	Aspects	Sub Aspects	Weight/ Highest Score	Ability			Supervision Criteria				
				Get	Get		Unable to	4	3	2	1
					With verbal language	With physical language		Get	With verbal language	With physical language	Unable to
1.	Introducing the flower bouquet making tool	1.1 Observing the tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scissors • Pliers • Glue Gun • <i>Cutter</i> 	4	0	0	0	0				
		1.2 Show tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scissors • Pliers • Glue Gun • <i>Cutter</i> 	4	0	0	0	0				
		1.3 Mention of tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scissors • Pliers • Glue Gun • <i>Cutter</i> 	4	0	0	0	0				
		1.4 Distinguishing tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Distinguishing scissors from pliers</i> • <i>Distinguishing glue guns from glue candles</i> • <i>Distinguishing a cutter from a knife (validator 2)</i> 	4	0	0	0	0				
02	Introducing the materials for making a bouquet of flowers	2.1 Observe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Pipe Cleaner</i> • Skewers • Flower Soltifs • Paper Bouquet • Plastic Bouquet 	4	0	0	0	0				

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Styrofoam</i> • <i>Doubletip</i> • Wax Glue • Solatip • Ribbon 									
	<p>2.2 Show</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Pipe Cleaner</i> • Skewers • Flower Soltifs • Paper Bouquet • Plastic Bouquet • <i>Styrofoam</i> • <i>Doubletip</i> • Wax Glue • Solatip • Ribbon 	4	0	0	0	0				
	<p>2.3 Mention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Pipe Cleaner</i> • Skewers • Flower Soltifs • Paper Bouquet • Plastic Bouquet • <i>Styrofoam</i> • <i>Doubletip</i> • Wax Glue • Solatip • Ribbon 	4	0	0	0	0				
	<p>2.4 Differentiate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Distinguishing pipe cleaners from wire</i> • <i>Distinguishing skewers from skewers</i> • <i>Distinguishing flower solatyps from ribbons</i> • <i>Distinguishing paper bouquets from plastic bouquets</i> • <i>Distinguishing styrofoam from foam</i> • <i>Distinguishing a doubletip from a solatip</i> 	4	0	0	0	0				

		• <i>Distinguishing wax glue from paper glue (validator 2)</i>										
3.	Preparation of tools for making a bouquet of flowers	3.1 Preparing scissors	4	0	0	0	0					
		3.2 Preparing pliers	4	0	0	0	0					
		3.3 Setting up the glue gun	4	0	0	0	0					
		3.4 Setting up the cutter	4	0	0	0	0					
4.	Preparation of materials for making a bouquet of flowers	4.1 Setting up a <i>pipe cleaner</i>	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.2 Preparing skewers	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.3 Preparing flower solatip	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.4 Preparing the bouquet paper	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.5 Plastic bouquet	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.6 Setting up the <i>styroform</i>	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.7 Prepare the solatip	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.8 Setting up a <i>doubletip</i>	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.9 Preparing wax glue	4	0	0	0	0					
		4.10 Setting up the ribbon	4	0	0	0	0					
5.	Implementation	5.1 Implementing OSH (occupational health and safety) (validator 1)	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.2 Holding both ends of the <i>pipe cleaner</i>	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.3 Folding the <i>pipe cleaner</i> to the same length	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.4 Taking scissors	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.5 Cut the <i>pipe cleaner</i> in half the same length (do it twice)	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.6 Picking up a cut <i>pipe cleaner</i>	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.7 Holding both ends of the <i>pipe cleaner</i>	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.8 Folding the <i>pipe cleaner</i> to the same length	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.9 Take one whole <i>pipe cleaner</i>	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.10 Insert the cut and folded <i>pipe cleaner</i> into the intact <i>pipe cleaner</i>	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.11 Fold the intact <i>pipe cleaner</i> crosswise upwards	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.12 Pull the end of the <i>pipe cleaner</i> that has been crossed down	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.13 Tidy up the <i>clenaer pipe</i> so that it forms flower petals	3	0	0	0	0					
		5.14 Take one end of the <i>pipe cleaner</i> and wrap it around it to lock it so that it is neat	3	0	0	0	0					

5.15	Bending <i>the cleaner pipe</i> so that it forms flower petals	3	0	0	0	0				
5.16	Remake the petals according to the steps above as many as 6 pieces	3	0	0	0	0				
5.17	Bringing all the petals together into a whole flower	3	0	0	0	0				
5.18	Picking up the glue gun	3	0	0	0	0				
5.19	Inserting wax glue into the glue shot tool	3	0	0	0	0				
5.20	Heating the glue gun	3	0	0	0	0				
5.21	Apply the hot glue gun to the center of the petals	3	0	0	0	0				
5.22	Waiting for the glue gun to dry	3	0	0	0	0				
5.23	Take a skewer	3	0	0	0	0				
5.24	Putting flowers and skewers together using glue guns	3	0	0	0	0				
5.25	Taking flower solatip	3	0	0	0	0				
5.26	Taking scissors	3	0	0	0	0				
5.27	Cutting the solatip according to needs	3	0	0	0	0				
5.28	Wrap the flower solatip on a skewer	3	0	0	0	0				
5.29	Make a few flower stalks according to the steps above	3	0	0	0	0				
5.30	Taking <i>styrofoam</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.31	Picking up <i>the cutter</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.32	Cutting <i>the styrofoam</i> into two parts	3	0	0	0	0				
5.33	<i>Cut the styrofoam that has been split in half into four parts (validator 1)</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.34	Stacking four pieces of <i>styrofoam</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.35	Taking a solatip	3	0	0	0	0				
5.36	Taking scissors	3	0	0	0	0				
5.37	Putting together four <i>stacked styrofoam</i> pieces	3	0	0	0	0				
5.38	Wrap the solatip on the right and left sides	3	0	0	0	0				
5.39	Cutting the solatip as needed	3	0	0	0	0				
5.40	Picking up a few flower stalks	3	0	0	0	0				
5.41	Thrust the flower stalks into <i>the styrofoam</i> as needed	3	0	0	0	0				
5.42	Picking up the bouquet paper	3	0	0	0	0				
5.43	Picking up <i>the cutter</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.44	Folding the bouquet paper into two equal lengths	3	0	0	0	0				
5.45	Cutting the bouquet paper with <i>a cutter</i> into two parts	3	0	0	0	0				

5.46	Take a piece of bouquet paper that has been cut	3	0	0	0	0				
5.47	Folds back into two equal lengths	3	0	0	0	0				
5.48	Cutting bouquet paper using <i>a cutter</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.49	Picking up a new bouquet of paper	3	0	0	0	0				
5.50	Folding the bouquet paper into two equal parts	3	0	0	0	0				
5.51	Cutting bouquet paper using <i>a cutter</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.52	Fold each bouquet paper into three pieces	3	0	0	0	0				
5.53	Cutting the bouquet paper using <i>a cutter</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.54	Picking up a whole bouquet of paper	3	0	0	0	0				
5.55	Folding both sides of the bottom of the paper bouquet	3	0	0	0	0				
5.56	Taking a solatip	3	0	0	0	0				
5.57	Gluing both sides of the bottom of the bouquet paper using a solatype	3	0	0	0	0				
5.58	Attaching the bouquet paper to the back side of <i>the styrofoam</i>	3	0	0	0	0				
5.59	Picking up the bouquet paper that has been divided in half	3	0	0	0	0				
5.60	Fold both sides of the bouquet paper to the center	3	0	0	0	0				
5.61	Taking a solatip	3	0	0	0	0				
5.62	Taking scissors	3	0	0	0	0				
5.63	Cutting solatips as needed	3	0	0	0	0				
5.64	Attaching a solatype to a bouquet of paper	3	0	0	0	0				
5.65	Attaching the bouquet paper to the left side of the bouquet	3	0	0	0	0				
5.66	Attaching the bouquet paper to the right side of the bouquet	3	0	0	0	0				
5.67	Folding the fan-shaped bouquet paper	3	0	0	0	0				
5.68	Attach a fan-shaped bouquet paper to the front of the bouquet	3	0	0	0	0				
5.69	Picking up a plastic bouquet	3	0	0	0	0				
5.70	Do the same as the steps when attaching the bouquet paper	3	0	0	0	0				
5.71	Picking up the ribbon	3	0	0	0	0				
5.72	Taking scissors	3	0	0	0	0				
5.73	Cut the ribbon as needed	3	0	0	0	0				
5.74	Wrapping the ribbon around the bouquet	3	0	0	0	0				
5.75	Tying the ribbon rope forming a ribbon	3	0	0	0	0				

6.	Maintain the appliance	6.1	Storing used scissors	4	0	0	0	0				
		6.2	Storing used pliers	4	0	0	0	0				
		6.3	Storing <i>used</i> cutters	4	0	0	0	0				
		6.4	Storing used flower glue	4	0	0	0	0				
7.	Preserving materials	7.1	Storing <i>pipe cleaners</i> in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.2	Storing the solatype in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.3	Storing flower solatips in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.4	Storing the ribbon in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.5	Storing bouquet paper in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.6	Storing plastic bouquets in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.7	Storing <i>styrofoam</i> in place	4	0	0	0	0				
		7.8	<i>Cleaning up used skill spaces (validator 1)</i>	4	0	0	0	0				
8.	Maintaining yield 	8.1	Storing a bouquet of flowers on a prepared shelf	4	0	0	0	0				

Note: ***Bolded and italicized sentences validated from different schools***

2. Research Discussion

This study discusses the preparation of task analysis. According to Astaty and Mulyati, (2010:15) stated that "Children with mild intellectual disabilities are children whose IQ ranges from 50-70. Children including the mild intellectual disabled are those who have the ability to develop in academics, social adjustment, and ability". Researchers have conducted field studies through observations, interviews and documentation studies about learning the skills of making flower bouquets made of *pipe cleaners for children with intellectual disabilities* in class IX at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City, in terms of learning skills that must be mastered, namely the steps to make flower bouquets starting from getting to know the tools, getting to know the materials, the steps to work, maintaining the tools, maintaining the materials, and maintain the results. During skill learning, there are obstacles or obstacles, because each child has different abilities. Some children still do not know colors, while some other children experience obstacles in fine motor skills so that during the process the child still looks stiff and still needs the help of the teacher. The tool used to make it easier for children to learn skills and make it easier for teachers to assess children's abilities is through task analysis, because task analysis is an activity to detail complex tasks into as detailed and simple as possible so that it can make it easier for children to understand a learning. This is in line with Sudrajat and Rosida (2013:101) "task analysis is a technique of breaking down a task or activity into small steps in sequence and teaching each step so that children can do it all". In the implementation of the practice of making flower bouquets, teachers are assisted by children to prepare tools and materials. Before starting the practice, the teacher introduces the tools and materials to the children. Furthermore, the teacher asked the children to pay attention to the process of making a bouquet of flowers that will be practiced. After the child notices, then practice it and be accompanied by a teacher so that children who feel difficulties can be helped by a companion teacher. In carrying out the process of making a bouquet of flowers, the child has carried out quite well even though there are several steps that must be helped.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusions and recommendations in this study are as follows:

1. Conclusion

Based on theoretical studies and reality in the field, researchers can draw conclusions from the analysis of the learning task of making flower bouquets made of *pipe cleaners* carried out at SLB BC YPLAB Wartawan Bandung City. Description of the results and discussion that the task analysis is effective in the skill of making flower bouquets made of *pipe cleaner* for children with mild intellectual disabilities class IX. From the results of observations, interviews, documentation studies, FGD (*Focus Group Discussion*), and validation, data on children's abilities and children's learning needs were obtained, so that they can be a reference in compiling task analysis. By using task analysis, it can make it easier for children with mild intellectual disabilities to receive learning materials and make it easier for teachers to assess children's abilities.

2. Recommendations

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted in the study, the researcher made the following recommendations;

a. For Teachers

Based on the results of the study, the researcher suggested to teachers to use task analysis techniques as a learning skill in making flower bouquets in children with mild intellectual disabilities in grade IX, where each component will be broken down into sub-sub-components to make it easier for children with mild intellectual disabilities to demonstrate and teachers are also easy to give assessments so that the evaluation obtained is clearer.

b. For Schools

This research is expected to be a reference for schools in the preparation of task analysis, so that the school can further develop the material and a wider population in the school.

c. For Researchers

This research is expected to be useful to increase knowledge, insight, and in-depth experience for researchers regarding the preparation of task analysis, as well as to develop the knowledge that has been obtained while in college.

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